
ON BINOMIAL COEFFICIENTS MODULO SQUARES OF PRIMES

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Received: 12/6/17, Revised: 10/8/18, Accepted: 1/6/19, Published: 2/1/19

Abstract

We give elementary proofs for the Apagodu-Zeilberger-Stanton-Amdeberhan-Tauraso congruences

$$\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \binom{2n}{n} \equiv \eta_p \sum_{n=0}^{r-1} \binom{2n}{n} \pmod{p^2},$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \sum_{m=0}^{sp-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 \equiv \eta_p \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 \pmod{p^2},$$

where p is an odd prime, r and s are nonnegative integers, and

$$\eta_p = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \\ -1, & \text{if } p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}. \end{cases}$$

1. Introduction

In this note, we prove that any odd prime p and any $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfy

$$\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \binom{2n}{n} \equiv \eta_p \sum_{n=0}^{r-1} \binom{2n}{n} \pmod{p^2} \quad (\text{Theorem 3});$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \sum_{m=0}^{sp-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 \equiv \eta_p \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 \pmod{p^2} \quad (\text{Theorem 4}),$$

where

$$\eta_p = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \\ -1, & \text{if } p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}. \end{cases}$$

These two congruences are (slightly extended) versions of the “Super-Conjectures” 1’’ and 4’ stated by Apagodu and Zeilberger in [3]¹. Our proofs are more elementary than previous proofs by Stanton [16], and Amdeberhan and Tauraso [1].

A more detailed version of the present paper is available on the arXiv [10].

1.1. Binomial Coefficients

Let us first recall the definition of binomial coefficients.²

Definition 1. Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $m \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then, the *binomial coefficient* $\binom{m}{n}$ is a rational number defined by

$$\binom{m}{n} = \begin{cases} \frac{m(m-1)\cdots(m-n+1)}{n!}, & \text{if } n \in \mathbb{N}; \\ 0, & \text{if } n \notin \mathbb{N}. \end{cases}$$

This is the definition used in [7] and [9]. Some authors follow other conventions instead.

The following proposition is well-known (see, e.g., [9, Proposition 1.9]), and will be tacitly used below (as we study congruences involving binomial coefficients).

Proposition 1. *We have $\binom{m}{n} \in \mathbb{Z}$ for any $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.*

1.2. Classical Congruences

The behavior of binomial coefficients modulo primes and prime powers is a classical subject of research; see [14, §2.1] for a survey of much of it. Let us state two of the most basic results in this subject.

Theorem 1. *Let p be a prime. Let a and b be two integers. Let c and d be two elements of $\{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. Then,*

$$\binom{ap+c}{bp+d} \equiv \binom{a}{b} \binom{c}{d} \pmod{p}.$$

Theorem 1 is known under the name of *Lucas’s theorem*, and is proven in many places (e.g., [14, §2.1], [11, Proof of §4], [2, proof of Lucas’s theorem] and [7, Exercise 5.61]) at least in the case when a and b are nonnegative integers. The standard proof of Theorem 1 in this case uses generating functions; this proof applies (*mutatis mutandis*) in the general case as well. See [9, Theorem 1.11] for an elementary proof of Theorem 1.

Another fundamental result is the following.

¹In the arXiv preprint version of [3] (<https://arxiv.org/abs/1606.03351v2>), these congruences appear as “Super-Conjectures” 1’’ and 5’, respectively.

²We use the notation \mathbb{N} for the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$.

Theorem 2. *Let p be a prime. Let a and b be two integers. Then,*

$$\binom{ap}{bp} \equiv \binom{a}{b} \pmod{p^2}.$$

Theorem 2 is a known result, often attributed to Charles Babbage. It appears with proof in [9, Theorem 1.12]; again, many sources prove it for nonnegative a and b (such as [15, Exercise 1.14 c] or [7, Exercise 5.62]). Notice that if $p \geq 5$, then the modulus p^2 can be replaced by p^3 or (depending on a , b and p) by even higher powers of p ; see [14, (22) and (23)] for the details. See also [17, Lemma 2.1] for another strengthening of Theorem 2.

1.3. Modulo- p^2 Congruences

Definition 2. For any $p \in \mathbb{Z}$, we define an integer $\eta_p \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ by

$$\eta_p = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \\ -1, & \text{if } p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}. \end{cases}$$

Notice that η_p is the so-called *Legendre symbol* $\left(\frac{p}{3}\right)$ known from number theory.

We are now ready to state two conjectures by Apagodu and Zeilberger, which we shall prove in the sequel. The first one is [3, Super-Conjecture 1'']:³

Theorem 3. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $r \in \mathbb{N}$. Set*

$$\alpha_r = \sum_{n=0}^{r-1} \binom{2n}{n}.$$

Then,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \binom{2n}{n} \equiv \eta_p \alpha_r \pmod{p^2}.$$

Theorem 3 has been proven by Dennis Stanton [16] using Laurent series (in the case when $p \geq 5$), and by Liu [12, (1.3)] using harmonic numbers. We shall reprove it elementarily. Note that we can apply Theorem 3 to $r = 1$, and obtain the congruence $\sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \binom{2n}{n} \equiv \eta_p \pmod{p^2}$ for each odd prime p ; this is [3, Super-Conjecture 1].

The next conjecture that we shall prove is [3, Super-Conjecture 5'].

³To be precise (and boastful), our Theorem 3 is somewhat stronger than [3, Super-Conjecture 1''], since we only require p to be odd (rather than $p \geq 5$). The same remark applies to Theorem 4. That said, the $p = 3$ case may well fall prey to simpler methods.

Theorem 4. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $r \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in \mathbb{N}$. Set*

$$\epsilon_{r,s} = \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2.$$

Then,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \sum_{m=0}^{sp-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 \equiv \eta_p \epsilon_{r,s} \pmod{p^2}.$$

A proof of Theorem 4 has been found by Amdeberhan and Tauraso, and was outlined in [1, §6]; we give a different, elementary proof.

1.4. Bailey’s Congruence and Analogues

On our way to proving the above two theorems, we shall show a modulo- p^2 congruence for certain binomial coefficients that can be regarded as a counterpart to Theorem 2.

Theorem 5. *Let p be a prime. Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $K \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$. Then we have*

(a)

$$\binom{Np}{Kp+i} \equiv N \binom{N-1}{K} \binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2};$$

(b)

$$\binom{Np}{Kp-i} \equiv N \binom{N-1}{K-1} \binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2};$$

(c)

$$\binom{Np}{Kp+i} + \binom{Np}{Kp-i} \equiv N \binom{N}{K} \binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2}.$$

Theorem 5 (a) is essentially the result [4, Theorem 4] by Bailey (see also [14, (26)]); in fact, it transforms into [4, Theorem 4] if we rewrite $N \binom{N-1}{K}$ as $(K+1) \binom{N}{K+1}$ (using Proposition 8 below). We shall nevertheless give our own proof for it.

1.5. Polynomial Summation

Let us state two further lemmas that will be crucial to our proofs of Theorems 3 and 4, but are likely to have other uses as well.

Let $\mathbb{Z}[X]$ be the ring of all polynomials in one indeterminate X with integer coefficients. It is well-known that all integers p , c and l and every polynomial $P \in$

$\mathbb{Z}[X]$ satisfy $P(cp + l) \equiv P(l) \pmod{p}$. Thus, polynomials in $\mathbb{Z}[X]$ can be applied to modulo- p congruences, yielding new modulo- p congruences. More interesting is the fact that sometimes polynomials can be used to turn modulo- p congruences into modulo- p^2 congruences. Two vehicles for such “lifting” of congruences are the following two lemmas (proven further below).

Lemma 1. *Let p be a prime. Let $c \in \mathbb{Z}$. Let $P \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$ be a polynomial of degree $< 2p - 1$. Then, $\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (P(cp + l) - P(l)) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$.*

Lemma 2. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $c \in \mathbb{Z}$. Let $P \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$ be a polynomial of degree $\leq p - 1$. Then,*

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (P(cp + l) - P(l)) P(l) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

2. The Proofs

2.1. Identities and Congruences From the Literature

Before we come to the proofs of the above-listed results, let us collect various well-known facts that will prove useful.

We assume that the reader is familiar with standard properties of binomial coefficients (see, e.g., [8, §3.1], [7, Chapter 5] or [9, §1]):

Proposition 2. *We have $\binom{m}{n} = 0$ for every $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfying $m < n$.*

Proposition 3. *Let $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfy $m \geq n$. Then, $\binom{m}{n} = \binom{m}{m-n}$.*

Proposition 4. *Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, $\binom{m}{n} = (-1)^n \binom{n-m-1}{n}$.*

Proposition 5. *Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then, $\binom{m}{n} = \binom{m-1}{n-1} + \binom{m-1}{n}$.*

Proposition 6. *For every $x \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $y \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have*

$$\binom{x+y}{n} = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{x}{k} \binom{y}{n-k}.$$

Proposition 6 is the so-called *Vandermonde convolution identity*, and is a particular case of [8, Theorem 3.29].

Proposition 7. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^i \binom{n-1-i}{i} = (-1)^n \cdot \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ -1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}. \end{cases}$$

Proposition 7 is [8, Corollary 8.68]. Apart from that, Proposition 7 can be easily derived from [7, §5.2, Problem 3], [5, Identity 172] or [6].

Proposition 8. Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then, $k \binom{n}{k} = n \binom{n-1}{k-1}$.

Proposition 8 (sometimes known as the “absorption identity”) appears in [7, (5.6)], and is easily proven just from the definition of binomial coefficients.

Let us also recall a result from elementary number theory:

Theorem 6. Let p be a prime. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Assume that k is not a positive multiple of $p-1$. Then,

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} l^k \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

Theorem 6 is proven, e.g., in [9, Theorem 3.1] and (in a slightly rewritten form) in [13, Theorem 1].

2.2. Variants and Consequences of Vandermonde Convolution

We are now going to state a number of identities that are restatements or particular cases of the Vandermonde convolution identity (Proposition 6). We begin with the following one.

Corollary 1. Let $u \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $l \in \mathbb{N}$ and $w \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,

$$\sum_{m=0}^l \binom{u}{w+m} \binom{l}{m} = \binom{u+l}{w+l}.$$

Proof of Corollary 1. Proposition 6 (applied to $x = u$, $y = l$ and $n = w + l$) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{u+l}{w+l} &= \sum_{k=0}^{w+l} \binom{u}{k} \binom{l}{w+l-k} = \sum_{k=0}^{w-1} \binom{u}{k} \underbrace{\binom{l}{w+l-k}}_{=0} + \sum_{k=w}^{w+l} \binom{u}{k} \binom{l}{w+l-k} \\ &\quad \text{(by Proposition 2} \\ &\quad \text{(since } l < w+l-k \\ &\quad \text{(because } k < w)) \\ &= \sum_{k=w}^{w+l} \binom{u}{k} \binom{l}{w+l-k} = \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{u}{w+m} \underbrace{\binom{l}{w+l-(w+m)}}_{= \binom{l}{l-m} = \binom{l}{m}} \\ &\quad \text{(by Proposition 3)} \end{aligned}$$

(here, we have substituted $w + m$ for k in the sum)

$$= \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{u}{w+m} \binom{l}{m}.$$

This proves Corollary 1. □

Let us also state another corollary of Proposition 6.

Corollary 2. *Let $x \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $y \in \mathbb{N}$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then,*

$$\binom{x+y}{n} = \sum_{i=0}^y \binom{x}{n-i} \binom{y}{i}.$$

See [9, Corollary 2.2] for a proof of Corollary 2.

Lemma 3. *Let $u \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $w \in \mathbb{N}$ and $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$\binom{u+2l}{w+l} = \binom{u}{w} \binom{2l}{l} + \sum_{i=1}^l \left(\binom{u}{w+i} + \binom{u}{w-i} \right) \binom{2l}{l-i}.$$

Proof of Lemma 3. Corollary 2 (applied to $x = u$, $y = 2l$ and $n = w + l$) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{u+2l}{w+l} &= \sum_{i=0}^{2l} \binom{u}{w+l-i} \binom{2l}{i} = \sum_{i=-l}^l \binom{u}{w+i} \binom{2l}{l-i} \\ &\quad \text{(here, we have substituted } l-i \text{ for } i \text{ in the sum)} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{i \in \{-l, -l+1, \dots, l\}; \\ i \neq 0}} \binom{u}{w+i} \binom{2l}{l-i} + \binom{u}{w} \binom{2l}{l} \end{aligned}$$

(here, we have split off the addend for $i = 0$ from the sum). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{u+2l}{w+l} - \binom{u}{w} \binom{2l}{l} &= \sum_{\substack{i \in \{-l, -l+1, \dots, l\}; \\ i \neq 0}} \binom{u}{w+i} \binom{2l}{l-i} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^l \binom{u}{w+i} \binom{2l}{l-i} + \sum_{i=-l}^{-1} \binom{u}{w+i} \binom{2l}{l-i} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^l \binom{u}{w+i} \binom{2l}{l-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \binom{u}{w-i} \underbrace{\binom{2l}{l+i}}_{\substack{= \binom{2l}{l-i} \\ \text{(by Proposition 3)}}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{here, we have substituted } -i \text{ for } i \\ \text{in the second sum} \end{array} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^l \left(\binom{u}{w+i} + \binom{u}{w-i} \right) \binom{2l}{l-i}. \end{aligned}$$

Adding $\binom{u}{w} \binom{2l}{l}$ to both sides yields the claim of Lemma 3. □

Lemma 4. *Let $p \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $c \in \mathbb{Z}$. Let $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. Then,*

$$\binom{cp+2l}{l} = \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{cp+l}{k} \binom{l}{k}.$$

Proof of Lemma 4. Corollary 2 (applied to $x = cp + l$, $y = l$ and $n = l$) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{cp+2l}{l} &= \sum_{i=0}^l \binom{cp+l}{l-i} \binom{l}{i} = \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{cp+l}{k} \underbrace{\binom{l}{l-k}}_{= \binom{l}{k}} \\ & \hspace{10em} \text{(by Proposition 3)} \end{aligned}$$

(here, we have substituted k for $l - i$ in the sum)

$$= \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{cp+l}{k} \binom{l}{k}.$$

Comparing this with

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{cp+l}{k} \binom{l}{k} &= \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{cp+l}{k} \binom{l}{k} + \sum_{k=l+1}^{p-1} \binom{cp+l}{k} \underbrace{\binom{l}{k}}_{=0} \\ & \hspace{10em} \text{(by Proposition 2} \\ & \hspace{10em} \text{(applied to } m=l \text{ and } n=k) \\ & \hspace{10em} \text{(since } l < k)) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{cp+l}{k} \binom{l}{k}, \end{aligned}$$

we obtain $\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{cp+l}{k} \binom{l}{k} = \binom{cp+2l}{l}$. This proves Lemma 4. □

Lemma 5. *Let $p \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$\sum_{i=1}^l \binom{p}{i} \binom{2l}{l-i} = \binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l}.$$

Proof of Lemma 5. Proposition 6 (applied to $x = p, y = 2l$ and $n = l$) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{p+2l}{l} &= \sum_{k=0}^l \binom{p}{k} \binom{2l}{l-k} = \sum_{i=0}^l \binom{p}{i} \binom{2l}{l-i} \\ &\quad \text{(here, we have renamed the summation index } k \text{ as } i) \\ &= \underbrace{\binom{p}{0} \binom{2l}{l-0}}_{=1} + \sum_{i=1}^l \binom{p}{i} \binom{2l}{l-i} = \binom{2l}{l} + \sum_{i=1}^l \binom{p}{i} \binom{2l}{l-i}. \\ &\quad = \binom{2l}{l} \end{aligned}$$

Solving this equality for $\sum_{i=1}^l \binom{p}{i} \binom{2l}{l-i}$, we obtain Lemma 5. □

2.3. Proof of Bailey’s Congruence

Proof of Theorem 5. From $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$, we conclude that both $i-1$ and $p-i$ are elements of $\{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. Notice also that i is not divisible by p (since $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$); hence, i is coprime to p (since p is a prime). Therefore, i is also coprime to p^2 .

(a) Proposition 8 (applied to $n = Np$ and $k = Kp + i$) yields

$$\begin{aligned} (Kp+i) \binom{Np}{Kp+i} &= Np \binom{Np-1}{Kp+i-1} = Np \underbrace{\binom{(N-1)p+(p-1)}{Kp+(i-1)}}_{\equiv \binom{N-1}{K} \binom{p-1}{i-1} \pmod{p}} \\ &\quad \text{(by Theorem 1, applied to } a=N-1, b=K, c=p-1 \text{ and } d=i-1) \\ &\equiv Np \binom{N-1}{K} \binom{p-1}{i-1} \pmod{p^2} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

(notice that the presence of the p factor has turned a congruence modulo p into a congruence modulo p^2). Thus,

$$(Kp+i) \binom{Np}{Kp+i} \equiv Np \binom{N-1}{K} \binom{p-1}{i-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p},$$

so that $0 \equiv \underbrace{(Kp+i)}_{\equiv i \pmod{p}} \binom{Np}{Kp+i} \equiv i \binom{Np}{Kp+i} \pmod{p}$. We can cancel i from this

congruence (since i is coprime to p), and thus obtain $0 \equiv \binom{Np}{Kp+i} \pmod{p}$. Hence,

$\binom{Np}{Kp+i}$ is divisible by p . Thus, $p\binom{Np}{Kp+i}$ is divisible by p^2 . In other words,

$$p\binom{Np}{Kp+i} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}. \tag{2}$$

Now,

$$(Kp+i)\binom{Np}{Kp+i} = Kp\underbrace{\binom{Np}{Kp+i}}_{\substack{\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by (2))}}} + i\binom{Np}{Kp+i} \equiv i\binom{Np}{Kp+i} \pmod{p^2}.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} i\binom{Np}{Kp+i} &\equiv (Kp+i)\binom{Np}{Kp+i} \equiv Np\binom{N-1}{K}\binom{p-1}{i-1} && \text{(by (1))} \\ &= N\binom{N-1}{K}\underbrace{p\binom{p-1}{i-1}}_{=i\binom{p}{i}} = N\binom{N-1}{K}i\binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2}. && \text{(by Proposition 8)} \end{aligned}$$

We can cancel i from this congruence (since i is coprime to p^2), and thus obtain

$$\binom{Np}{Kp+i} \equiv N\binom{N-1}{K}\binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2}.$$

This proves Theorem 5 (a).

(b) We have $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ and thus $p-i \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$. Hence, Theorem 5 (a) (applied to $K-1$ and $p-i$ instead of K and i) yields

$$\binom{Np}{(K-1)p+(p-i)} \equiv N\binom{N-1}{K-1}\underbrace{\binom{p}{p-i}}_{=i\binom{p}{i}} = N\binom{N-1}{K-1}\binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2}. \tag{by Proposition 3}$$

In view of $(K-1)p+(p-i) = Kp-i$, this can be rewritten as

$$\binom{Np}{Kp-i} \equiv N\binom{N-1}{K-1}\binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2}.$$

This proves Theorem 5 (b).

positive multiple of $p - 1$. Thus, Theorem 6 (applied to $k - 1$ instead of k) yields $\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} l^{k-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Thus, $p \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} l^{k-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$, so that

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (P(cp+l) - P(l)) \equiv kcp \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} l^{k-1}}_{\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

This proves Lemma 1. □

Lemma 6. *Let p, a and b be integers such that $a - b$ is divisible by p . Then, $a^2 - b^2 \equiv 2(a - b)b \pmod{p^2}$.*

Proof of Lemma 6. The difference $(a^2 - b^2) - 2(a - b)b = (a - b)^2$ is divisible by p^2 (since $a - b$ is divisible by p). In other words, $a^2 - b^2 \equiv 2(a - b)b \pmod{p^2}$. Lemma 6 is proven. □

Proof of Lemma 2. Fix $l \in \mathbb{Z}$. We have $P \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$. Thus, $P(u) - P(v)$ is divisible by $u - v$ whenever u and v are two integers⁴. Applying this to $u = cp + l$ and $v = l$, we conclude that $P(cp + l) - P(l)$ is divisible by $(cp + l) - l = cp$, and thus also divisible by p . Hence, Lemma 6 (applied to $a = P(cp + l)$ and $b = P(l)$) yields

$$(P(cp+l))^2 - (P(l))^2 \equiv 2(P(cp+l) - P(l))P(l) \pmod{p^2}. \tag{3}$$

Now, forget that we fixed l . We thus have proven (3) for each $l \in \mathbb{Z}$.

The polynomial P has degree $\leq p - 1$. Hence, the polynomial P^2 has degree $\leq 2(p - 1) < 2p - 1$. Thus, Lemma 1 (applied to P^2 instead of P) shows that

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (P^2(cp+l) - P^2(l)) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

Thus,

$$0 \equiv \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \underbrace{(P^2(cp+l) - P^2(l))}_{\substack{=(P(cp+l))^2 - (P(l))^2 \\ \equiv 2(P(cp+l) - P(l))P(l) \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by (3))}}} \equiv 2 \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (P(cp+l) - P(l))P(l) \pmod{p^2}.$$

We can cancel 2 from this congruence (since p is odd), and conclude that

$$0 \equiv \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (P(cp+l) - P(l))P(l) \pmod{p^2}.$$

This proves Lemma 2. □

⁴This is a well-known fact, and easily proven.

2.5. Applying Lemma 2

Now, let us prepare for the proofs of our results by showing several lemmas.

Lemma 7. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $c \in \mathbb{Z}$. Let $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, p - 1\}$. Then,*

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{cp+l}{k} - \binom{l}{k} \right) \binom{l}{k} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Lemma 7. Notice that $k!$ is coprime to p (since $k \leq p - 1$), and thus $k!^2$ is coprime to p^2 .

Define a polynomial $P \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$ by $P = X(X - 1) \cdots (X - k + 1)$. Then, P has degree $k \leq p - 1$. Thus, Lemma 2 yields

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (P(cp+l) - P(l)) P(l) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

Since each $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfies $P(n) = n(n - 1) \cdots (n - k + 1) = k! \binom{n}{k}$, this can be rewritten as

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(k! \binom{cp+l}{k} - k! \binom{l}{k} \right) k! \binom{l}{k} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

We can cancel $k!^2$ from this congruence (since $k!^2$ is coprime to p^2), and thus obtain

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{cp+l}{k} - \binom{l}{k} \right) \binom{l}{k} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

This proves Lemma 7. □

Lemma 8. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $c \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then,*

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{cp+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Lemma 8. For each $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p - 1\}$, we have

$$\underbrace{\binom{cp+2l}{l}}_{= \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{cp+l}{k} \binom{l}{k} \text{ (by Lemma 4)}} - \underbrace{\binom{2l}{l}}_{= \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{l}{k} \binom{l}{k} \text{ (by Lemma 4, applied to 0 instead of c)}} = \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{cp+l}{k} - \binom{l}{k} \right) \binom{l}{k}.$$

Summing these equalities over all $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p - 1\}$, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{cp+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) &= \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{cp+l}{k} - \binom{l}{k} \right) \binom{l}{k} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{cp+l}{k} - \binom{l}{k} \right) \binom{l}{k}}_{\substack{\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by Lemma 7)}}} \equiv \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} 0 = 0 \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves Lemma 8. □

2.6. η_p Appears

Let us now prove the particular case of Theorem 3 for $r = 1$:

Theorem 7. *Let p be an odd prime. Then,*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \binom{2n}{n} \equiv \eta_p \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Theorem 7. Lemma 8 (applied to $c = -1$) yields

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{-p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

Moving all the $\binom{2l}{l}$ addends to the right-hand side of this congruence, we obtain

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{-p+2l}{l} \equiv \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{2l}{l} \pmod{p^2}. \tag{4}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \binom{2n}{n} &= \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{2l}{l} \equiv \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \underbrace{\binom{-p+2l}{l}}_{\substack{= (-1)^l \binom{l - (-p+2l) - 1}{l} \\ \text{(by Proposition 4)}}} \tag{by (4)} \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (-1)^l \underbrace{\binom{l - (-p+2l) - 1}{l}}_{= \binom{p-1-l}{l}} = \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} (-1)^l \binom{p-1-l}{l} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} (-1)^i \binom{p-1-i}{i} = \underbrace{(-1)^p}_{=-1 \text{ (since } p \text{ is odd)}} \cdot \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ -1, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } p \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \end{cases} \\
 &\quad \text{(by Proposition 7, applied to } n = p) \\
 &= - \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ -1, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } p \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}; \\ -1, & \text{if } p \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \end{cases} = \eta_p \pmod{p^2}. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

2.7. Proving Theorem 3

Lemma 9. *Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $K \in \mathbb{N}$. Let p be a prime. Let $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. Then,*

$$\binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l} \equiv N \binom{N}{K} \left(\binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Lemma 9. Theorem 2 yields $\binom{Np}{Kp} \equiv \binom{N}{K} \pmod{p^2}$.

Lemma 3 (applied to $u = Np$ and $w = Kp$) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 \binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} &= \underbrace{\binom{Np}{Kp}}_{\equiv \binom{N}{K} \pmod{p^2}} \binom{2l}{l} + \sum_{i=1}^l \underbrace{\left(\binom{Np}{Kp+i} + \binom{Np}{Kp-i} \right)}_{\equiv N \binom{N}{K} \binom{p}{i} \pmod{p^2} \text{ (by Theorem 5 (c))}} \binom{2l}{l-i} \\
 &\equiv \binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l} + \sum_{i=1}^l N \binom{N}{K} \binom{p}{i} \binom{2l}{l-i} \\
 &= \binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l} + N \binom{N}{K} \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^l \binom{p}{i} \binom{2l}{l-i}}_{= \binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \text{ (by Lemma 5)}} \\
 &= \binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l} + N \binom{N}{K} \left(\binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) \pmod{p^2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Subtracting $\binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l}$ from both sides of this congruence, we obtain the exact claim of Lemma 9. □

Lemma 10. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $K \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} \equiv \binom{N}{K} \eta_p \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Lemma 10. For any $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$, we have (by Lemma 9)

$$\binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} \equiv \binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l} + N \binom{N}{K} \left(\binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) \pmod{p^2}.$$

Summing these congruences over all $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$, we prove Lemma 10:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} &\equiv \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l} + N \binom{N}{K} \left(\binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) \right) \\ &= \binom{N}{K} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{2l}{l} + N \binom{N}{K} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right)}_{\substack{\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by Lemma 8, applied to } c=1)}} \\ &\equiv \binom{N}{K} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{2l}{l}}_{\substack{= \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \binom{2n}{n} \equiv \eta_p \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by Theorem 7)}}} \equiv \binom{N}{K} \eta_p \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of Theorem 3. The map $\{0, 1, \dots, p-1\} \times \{0, 1, \dots, r-1\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, rp-1\}$
 $(l, K) \mapsto Kp+l$

is a bijection (since each element of $\{0, 1, \dots, rp-1\}$ can be uniquely divided by p with remainder, and said remainder will belong to $\{0, 1, \dots, r-1\}$). Thus, we can substitute $Kp+l$ for n in the sum $\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \binom{2n}{n}$. This sum thus can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \binom{2n}{n} &= \underbrace{\sum_{(l,K) \in \{0,1,\dots,p-1\} \times \{0,1,\dots,r-1\}} \binom{2(Kp+l)}{Kp+l}}_{= \sum_{K=0}^{r-1} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1}} = \sum_{K=0}^{r-1} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{2Kp+2l}{Kp+l} \\ &= \sum_{K=0}^{r-1} \binom{2Kp+2l}{Kp+l} \equiv \sum_{K=0}^{r-1} \binom{2K}{K} \eta_p \pmod{p^2} \\ &\quad \text{(by Lemma 10, applied to } N=2K) \\ &\equiv \sum_{K=0}^{r-1} \binom{2K}{K} \eta_p = \alpha_r \eta_p = \eta_p \alpha_r \pmod{p^2}. \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \binom{2n}{n} = \alpha_r \end{aligned}$$

This proves Theorem 3. □

2.8. Proving Theorem 4

Lemma 11. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $K \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \left(\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right) \binom{l}{m} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Lemma 11. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \left(\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right) \binom{l}{m} \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \underbrace{\sum_{m=0}^l \binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} \binom{l}{m}}_{\substack{= \binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} \\ \text{(by Corollary 1,} \\ \text{applied to } u=Np+l \text{ and } w=Kp)}} - \binom{N}{K} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \underbrace{\sum_{m=0}^l \binom{l}{m} \binom{l}{m}}_{\substack{= \binom{2l}{l} \\ \text{(by Corollary 1,} \\ \text{applied to } u=l \text{ and } w=0)}} \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} - \binom{N}{K} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{2l}{l} \right) = \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \underbrace{\left(\binom{Np+2l}{Kp+l} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{2l}{l} \right)}_{\substack{\equiv N \binom{N}{K} \left(\binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right) \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by Lemma 9)}}} \\ &\equiv N \binom{N}{K} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \left(\binom{p+2l}{l} - \binom{2l}{l} \right)}_{\substack{\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by Lemma 8, applied to } c=1)}} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves Lemma 11. □

Lemma 12. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $K \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{Np+l}{Kp+m}^2 \equiv \binom{N}{K}^2 \eta_p \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Lemma 12. Fix $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ and $m \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. Then, Theorem 1 (applied to $a = N$, $b = K$, $c = l$ and $d = m$) yields that $\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} \equiv \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \pmod{p}$. In other words, $\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m}$ is divisible by p . Hence,

Lemma 6 (applied to $a = \binom{Np+l}{Kp+m}$ and $b = \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m}$) shows that

$$\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m}^2 - \left(\binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right)^2 \equiv 2 \left(\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right) \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \pmod{p^2}. \tag{5}$$

Now, forget that we fixed l and m . We thus have proven (5) for all $l \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ and $m \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{Np+l}{Kp+m}^2 - \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \left(\binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right)^2 \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \underbrace{\left(\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m}^2 - \left(\binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right)^2 \right)}_{\equiv 2 \left(\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right) \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \pmod{p^2} \text{ (by (5))}} \\ &\equiv 2 \binom{N}{K} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \left(\binom{Np+l}{Kp+m} - \binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right) \binom{l}{m}}_{\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2} \text{ (by Lemma 11)}} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{Np+l}{Kp+m}^2 &\equiv \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \left(\binom{N}{K} \binom{l}{m} \right)^2 = \binom{N}{K}^2 \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \underbrace{\sum_{m=0}^l \binom{l}{m}^2}_{= \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{l}{m} \binom{l}{m} = \binom{2l}{l} \text{ (by Corollary 1, applied to } u=l \text{ and } w=0)} \\ &= \binom{N}{K}^2 \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \binom{2l}{l}}_{= \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \binom{2n}{n} \equiv \eta_p \pmod{p^2} \text{ (by Theorem 7)}} \\ &\equiv \binom{N}{K}^2 \eta_p \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves Lemma 12. □

Lemma 13. *Let p be a prime. Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $K \in \mathbb{Z}$. Let u and v be two elements of $\{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ satisfying $u+v \geq p$. Then, $p \mid \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}$.*

Proof of Lemma 13. We have $u+v \geq p$. Thus, $u+v = p+c$ for some $c \in \mathbb{N}$. Consider this c . From $v \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$, we obtain $v < p$. Thus, $c+p = p+c = u + \underbrace{v}_{< p} < u+p$, so that $c < u \leq p-1$ (since $u \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$). Thus, $c \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ (since $c \in \mathbb{N}$). Also, $c < u$. Hence, Proposition 2 (applied to $m=c$ and $n=u$) yields $\binom{c}{u} = 0$.

Theorem 1 (applied to $a=N+1$, $b=K$ and $d=u$) yields

$$\binom{(N+1)p+c}{Kp+u} \equiv \binom{N+1}{K} \underbrace{\binom{c}{u}}_{=0} = 0 \pmod{p}.$$

In other words, $p \mid \binom{(N+1)p+c}{Kp+u}$. In view of $(N+1)p+c = Np + \underbrace{p+c}_{=u+v} = Np+u+v$, this can be rewritten as $p \mid \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}$. This proves Lemma 13. \square

Lemma 14. *Let p be an odd prime. Let $N \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $K \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$\sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{v=0}^{p-1} \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2 \equiv \binom{N}{K}^2 \eta_p \pmod{p^2}.$$

Proof of Lemma 14. If u and v are two elements of $\{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ satisfying $v \geq p-u$, then

$$\binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2} \tag{6}$$

5.

Hence, any $u \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ satisfies

$$\sum_{v=0}^{p-1} \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2 = \sum_{v=0}^{p-u-1} \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2 + \underbrace{\sum_{v=p-u}^{p-1} \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2}_{\substack{\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2} \\ \text{(by (6))}}}$$

⁵*Proof of (6):* Let u and v be two elements of $\{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ satisfying $v \geq p-u$. From $v \geq p-u$, we obtain $u+v \geq p$. Thus, Lemma 13 yields $p \mid \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}$. Hence, $p^2 \mid \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2$. This proves (6).

$$\equiv \sum_{v=0}^{p-u-1} \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2 = \sum_{l=u}^{p-1} \binom{Np+l}{Kp+u}^2 \pmod{p^2}$$

(here, we have substituted l for $u+v$ in the sum). Summing up these congruences for all $u \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{v=0}^{p-1} \binom{Np+u+v}{Kp+u}^2 \\ & \equiv \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{l=u}^{p-1} \binom{Np+l}{Kp+u}^2 = \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{u=0}^l \binom{Np+l}{Kp+u}^2 = \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{m=0}^l \binom{Np+l}{Kp+m}^2 \\ & = \sum_{l=0}^{p-1} \sum_{u=0}^l \binom{Np+l}{Kp+u}^2 \\ & \quad \text{(here, we have renamed the index } u \text{ as } m \text{ in the second sum)} \\ & \equiv \binom{N}{K}^2 \eta_p \pmod{p^2} \end{aligned}$$

(by Lemma 12). This proves Lemma 14. □

Proof of Theorem 4. First, let us observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{r,s} &= \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 = \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 = \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \sum_{L=0}^{r-1} \binom{K+L}{L}^2 \\ &= \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \sum_{L=0}^{r-1} \binom{K+L}{K}^2 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

(since Proposition 3 yields $\binom{K+L}{L} = \binom{K+L}{K}$ for all $K \in \mathbb{N}$ and $L \in \mathbb{N}$).

Each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfies

$$\sum_{m=0}^{sp-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 = \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \binom{n+Kp+u}{Kp+u}^2$$

(here, we have substituted $Kp+u$ for m in the sum, since the map

$$\begin{aligned} \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\} \times \{0, 1, \dots, s-1\} &\rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, sp-1\}, \\ (u, K) &\mapsto Kp+u \end{aligned}$$

is a bijection). Summing up this equality over all $n \in \{0, 1, \dots, rp-1\}$, we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \sum_{m=0}^{sp-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 = \sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \binom{n+Kp+u}{Kp+u}^2$$

$$= \sum_{v=0}^{p-1} \sum_{L=0}^{r-1} \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \binom{Lp+v+Kp+u}{Kp+u}^2$$

(here, we have substituted $Lp + v$ for n in the sum, since the map

$$\begin{aligned} \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\} \times \{0, 1, \dots, r-1\} &\rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, rp-1\}, \\ (v, L) &\mapsto Lp + v \end{aligned}$$

is a bijection).

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{rp-1} \sum_{m=0}^{sp-1} \binom{n+m}{m}^2 &= \underbrace{\sum_{v=0}^{p-1} \sum_{L=0}^{r-1} \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \binom{Lp+v+Kp+u}{Kp+u}^2}_{= \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \sum_{L=0}^{r-1} \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{v=0}^{p-1} \binom{(K+L)p+u+v}{Kp+u}^2} \\ &= \sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \sum_{L=0}^{r-1} \underbrace{\sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{v=0}^{p-1} \binom{(K+L)p+u+v}{Kp+u}^2}_{\equiv \binom{K+L}{K}^2 \eta_p \pmod{p^2}} \\ &\quad \text{(by Lemma 14, applied to } N=K+L\text{)} \\ &\equiv \underbrace{\sum_{K=0}^{s-1} \sum_{L=0}^{r-1} \binom{K+L}{K}^2}_{\substack{= \epsilon_{r,s} \\ \text{(by (7))}}} \eta_p = \epsilon_{r,s} \eta_p = \eta_p \epsilon_{r,s} \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves Theorem 4. □

Acknowledgments. Thanks to Doron Zeilberger and Roberto Tauraso for alerting me to [1] and [17].

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